

**Test Plan for Experiments to Provide Preliminary End-to-End Communication System
Performance of an Advanced Satellite System**

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ABSTRACT In order for users to have a full understanding of how state-of-the-art satellite technology can improve the quality and reduce the costs of space-based communications, users must be given the system performance in terms they understand. For example, most users do not care how fast data can be routed through the satellite bus. The users want to know how fast they can send their data and thus the cost of sending a given amount of data. The experiments described in this test plan will provide a preliminary characterization of the Advanced Communication Technology Satellite (ACTS) from the user's perspective. The tests are designed, executed, and analyzed according to the American National Standards X3.102 and X3.141. The performance parameter values estimated in this preliminary characterization experiment will be used in the full characterization experiment to define failure/non-performance outcome thresholds.

1. Background

During the Industrial Revolution, trains became an important part of society by transporting raw materials and finished products across the country. In the current Information Age, information networks play a role similar to trains in moving raw and processed data. These networks have become essential in daily business. For example, \$300 trillion are transferred electronically on a yearly basis worldwide [1], averaging more than \$9.5 million per second.

Since the beginning of satellite communications in the early 1960's, when Syncom 2 transmitted the first transatlantic television signals, communications satellites have contributed to the information explosion by making worldwide communications possible. Despite the extensive use of fiber optic cables, more than half of all overseas communication is performed by satellites [1].

The first satellites acted as simple repeaters. In fact, the United States' first experimental satellite launched in 1960, Echo, acted like a large "mirror." It consisted of a 100-ft-diameter sphere used to reflect the RF signals back to Earth. As satellites evolved, they provided on-board amplification. However, they still operated in a repeater mode requiring large gateway earth stations (ES) to provide additional signal strength and switching. These comparatively simple systems gave users a good understanding of their capabilities by providing the system's signal-to-noise ratio and the bandwidth.¹

The latest experimental communication satellite system launched in the United States, the Advanced Communication Technology Satellite (ACTS), performs signal regeneration and switching on-board the spacecraft, hopping and scanning spot beams, Ka-band operation, and demand assigned multiple access (DAMA). The use of these technologies provides several advantages. First, due to the spot beams and Ka-band operation, the size of the ES antenna can decrease while still providing the same level of performance. Second, having the switching on board the satellite facilitates the use of a mesh network, eliminating the need for a double hop as used in star networks. Third, the DAMA feature allows multiple users to "seize capacity from a system, use it, and return it when finished" [2]. A DAMA system can use fewer circuits to obtain a similar blocking grade of service compared to a system using preassigned circuits. The more consistent use of the system increases its effective system capacity. Finally, the technologies used on ACTS provide as much as three times the communications capacity for the same weight as currently used satellites, and are thus more cost effective [3]. Therefore, between the smaller and less complicated ESs and the pooling of circuits, technologies introduced on ACTS have the potential to decrease user costs.

For systems such as ACTS, users require different and additional performance information than was necessary with repeater satellite systems. For example, with the use of DAMA, users will now have to request capacity for each communication session initiated. This is called an access request. Depending on the system loading or the existing weather conditions, access may occur within a specified amount of time, or it may be denied or ignored. For a user that requires short access times or a zero probability of access denial, this may be intolerable. However, other users may not have such usage restrictions. Therefore, in order for users to make an informed decision on system usage, users will need to know these times and probabilities.

This test plan discusses experiments necessary to provide a preliminary characterization of the ACTS system in terms which interest users. The full experiment title is "Quantify ACTS End-to-End Communication System Performance." This experiment uses standards approved by the American National Standards Institute (ANSI) to define the end-to-end digital communication service provided by ACTS from the user's perspective. In order to properly calculate the failure probabilities defined in the ANSI standards for characterization purposes, the approximate value of several of the performance parameters must be known *a priori*. This is done by performing a preliminary characterization test - the subject of this test plan.

2. Test Plan Purpose and Summary

The ITS ACTS experiment is split into three testing periods. The first testing period, designated the Preliminary Experiment Period (PEP), determines the values of the performance parameters and lasts 1 month. The parameter values must be estimated prior to the second testing period for characterization purposes. The second testing period, designated the Full Experiment Period (FEP), is the "real" test. This test fully characterizes the ACTS/ES system under various ideal and degraded situations. This period lasts a total of 6 months. The final experiment period, designated the Lifelong Experiment Period (LEP), measures the degradation that may occur over the lifetime of the satellite system. This period extends from the end of the FEP to the end of the NASA's operation of the satellite. Sample tests are executed for a total of 8 hours each month.

This test plan describes the PEP tests that must be done before the FEP in order to estimate the value of several performance parameters a priori. These parameters must be known *a priori* in order to set thresholds for poor or non-delivered service. The thresholds are defined proportional to a "specified value" of a performance parameter. For example, access denial occurs when the duration of an individual access attempt exceeds three times the specified value of the parameter Access Time. The specified value of the Access Time, used in the FEP, equals the sample mean of the Access Time measured in the PEP.

The tests run in the PEP are similar to tests run for the full characterization experiment with the exception that the preliminary experiment is done for non-stressed link conditions and in a loop-back configuration. The non-stressed conditions include clear weather and low traffic. Therefore, referring to the Access Time example again, in times of extreme stress (heavy rain and/or heavy traffic), the system may take an unacceptable amount of time to form a communication session between two end points. This trial results in an access denial outcome.

The preliminary characterization test is an intrusive test consisting of a series of point-to-point measurements between pairs of end users to measure the performance parameters defined in ANSI standards X3.102 and X3.141 for the ACTS system. Section 3 summarizes these standards, Section 4 elaborates on the experiment design, and Section 5 presents the schedule for the PEP.

3. American National Standards X3.102 and X3.141

The American National Standards X3.102 and X3.141 together provide "a uniform means of describing the performance of data communication services from the point of view of data communications users" [4]. The first standard defines 21 performance parameters used to quantify various aspects of a digital communication system's performance. These parameters apply to all classes of digital data communication systems,

independent of topology, protocol, and other design characteristics [5]. The second standard specifies a uniform method for measuring the value of the X3.102 parameters.

3.1 ANSI X3.102

ANSI X3.102 was developed with the purpose of establishing "a uniform means of specifying, assessing, and comparing the performance of data communication systems and services from the point of view of the data communications users" [5]. The standard defines 21 performance parameters that define various aspects of a digital communication system. The parameters are defined with respect to a user-oriented, system-independent model of the data communication process. Section 3.1.1 describes the data communication process model and Section 3.1.2 describes the performance parameters.

3.1.1 Data Communication Process

The data communication process is accomplished by end users transferring information across a system. An end user can be either a human operator or an application program. The system consists of the physical and functional components (e.g., transmission facilities, switches, data terminal and protocols) providing users with the data communication service [5].

The location of the user/system interface must be such that one can determine if the user or the system generated a particular interface event. The particular element of the system that interfaces with the user varies with the type of user. For a human operator, the system element interface is called a data terminal equipment (DTE) and an example is a personal computer connected to a data network. Therefore, in this case, the user/system interface is the physical interface between the operator and the personal computer's keyboard. For an application program, the system element interface is usually the computer's operating system. In this case, the interface is the functional interface between the computer program and the operating system. In both of these cases, it is assumed that the user generates the data to be transferred. The standard shows two other cases for which a separate data medium is used [5]. The experiments utilize an application program interfacing with the UNIX operating system.

The transfer of information across the user/system interface is called an interface event. Typical events at the application program/operating system interface include issuing operating system calls or the setting/clearing of flags.

Specific interface events are system dependent. However, there are several events that are common to most communication systems. The standard defines 10 system-independent interface events, shown in Table 1, which are called reference events.² For example, in a voice telephone call, the system-dependent action of lifting the handset off hook corresponds to the system-independent reference event Access Request.

Table 1. Reference Events Defined in ANSI X3.102

Function	Reference Event
Access	Access Request Nonoriginating User Commitment System Blocking Signal User Blocking Signal Access Confirmation
User Information Transfer	Start of Block Transfer End of Block Transfer
Disengagement	Disengagement Request User Disengagement Blocking Signal Disengagement Confirmation

The reference events are used to define the beginning and ending of the primary data communication functions — access, user information transfer, and disengagement. For example, the access function begins with the reference event Access Request and ends with the event Access Confirmation. Figure 1 illustrates the primary functions and reference events for a typical communication session using ACTS.

Figure 1. Typical ACTS communication session profile.

Information transferred within a data communication system can be divided into two groups: user and overhead information. User information consists of information that is transferred from a source user to the system with the intent of being delivered to the destination user. For the ITS ACTS experiment, the transferred user information is a pseudo-random data file consisting of a given number of bytes of data. Overhead information consists of all information other than user information. Overhead information could be transferred to a system by the user to control internal system operations, transferred to the user by the system to report system status, or transferred within a system to coordinate joint operations such as data flow control.

In summary, the data communication process model consists of end users participating in a communication session, involving access, user information transfer, and disengagement functions, across a data communication system through an interface. The information transferred consists of user or overhead information, either of which causes interface events.

3.1.2 Performance Parameters

The standard defines 21 performance parameters, shown in Table 2, which quantify various aspects of a digital communication system's performance³. These parameters are divided into two categories: primary and ancillary.

The primary parameters describe the speed, reliability, and accuracy of the data communication session. The speed parameters are estimated from the time stamps taken at the reference events. For example, for the access function, time stamps are taken at the reference events Access Request and

Table 2. ANSI X3.102 Performance Parameters

Function	Primary Parameters			Ancillary Parameters
	Performance Criterion			
Access	Access Time	Incorrect Access Probability	Access Denial Probability Access Outage Probability	User Fraction of Access Time
User Information Transfer	Block Transfer Time	Bit Error Probability Bit Misdelivery Probability Extra Bit Probability Block Error Probability Block Misdelivery Probability Extra Block Probability	Bit Loss Probability Block Loss Probability	User Fraction of Block Transfer Time
Disengage.	Disengage. Time	Denial Disengagement Probability		User Fraction of Disengage. Time

Access Confirmation. The difference of the two time stamps is one sample of the performance parameter Access Time. This process is repeated several times and the sample mean is calculated to obtain an estimate of the access time for a given confidence level. The reliability and accuracy parameters are estimated by two methods. The majority of the user information transfer reliability and accuracy parameters are estimated by comparing the pseudo-random data transferred to the data received. The majority of the remaining accuracy and reliability parameters are estimated by the ratio of errored outcomes, usually due to a system threshold timeout, to the total number of attempts. Section 3 in ANSI X3.102 [5] should be consulted for full definitions of each of the performance parameters.

The ancillary parameters measure the influence of the user delays on the primary speed parameters. Since system manufacturers and system providers cannot control the speed with which users manipulate their system, the ancillary parameters provide a method to factor out the user's contribution to the speed parameters. Therefore, user-independent system speed values can be obtained by subtracting the measured ancillary parameter values from the measured primary speed parameter values.

3.2 ANSI X3.141

ANSI X3.141 specifies uniform/repeatable methods to measure the performance of a digital communication system in accordance with X3.102. The measurement process is split into four phases: Experiment Design, Data Extraction, Data Reduction, and Data Analysis.

The experiment design phase starts with defining an objective, which can range from characterizing a system to determining the health, or need for maintenance, of a system. Next, the parameters that pertain to the system in question are determined. Finally, the population that will be studied is described, including the number and conditions under which the samples are taken. After the extraction, reduction, and analysis of some data, this phase may be repeated if refinements must be made to the experiment design.

The data extraction phase monitors the signals transferred across a pair of user/system interfaces in real time. The nature and time of significant interface signals (reference events) are recorded in a chronological reference event history.

The data reduction phase processes the raw data from the data extraction phase to produce estimates of the selected performance parameters. For example, for the access/disengagement tests, this phase determines if each access attempt was successful, incorrect, denied, or an outage. For the successful access attempts, the reduction phase determines the access time's sample mean. For the user information transfer test, this phase determines if each bit and block transfer was successful, incorrect, lost, errored, or refused. Using the raw results, the reduction phase calculates parameters such as the Bit and Block Error Probability.

The data analysis phase examines the reduced data to determine the precision of the estimated parameters. If the precision received is less than required for the test, the data extraction/reduction/analysis phases are all repeated to obtain additional data.

4. Experiment Design

As defined in ANSI X3.141, experiment design starts with a general measurement objective and results in a detailed plan defining the information to be collected and the conditions under which it is to be collected. This section defines the experiment objective, the parameters to be measured, and the population used.

4.1 Experiment Objective

The objective of the experiment is to characterize and quantify the end-to-end performance of the digital communication service provided by ACTS from the end user's perspective. There are a couple of reasons for having such an objective. First, due to the addition of advanced technologies such as DAMA (demand assigned multiple access) and scanning spot beams on future communication satellites, users will require more performance information than they have required in the past. They will be interested in parameters such as access time and blocking probabilities, to name just a few. The experiment will measure and document the performance of an advanced communication satellite system for the users. Second, as part of the Department of Commerce, ITS is interested in improving trade opportunities for domestic companies and increasing competition in the U.S. The tests on ACTS are a part of a larger program at ITS whose ultimate goal is to develop national and international telecommunication performance standards to strengthen the use of advanced communication satellites in telecommunication networks, thereby enhancing the United States' competitiveness.

4.2 Performance Parameters Measured

The set of performance parameters measured for a given data communication system depend on the attributes of the system. Out of the 24 parameters discussed in Section 3.1.2, 19 are applicable to the ACTS experiment [6]. These parameters include

- Access Time
- User Fraction (UF) of Access Time
- Access Denial Probability
- Access Outage Probability
- Block Transfer Time
- UF of Block Transfer Time
- User Information Bit Transfer Rate
- UF of Input/Output Rate
- Bit Error Probability
- Bit Loss Probability
- Extra Bit Probability
- Block Error Probability

Extra Block Probability
 Block Loss Probability
 Transfer Denial Probability
 Source Disengagement Time
 UF of Source Disengagement
 Destination Disengagement Time
 UF of Destination Disengagement Time.

The validity of the estimated values for the above parameters depends on the number of samples taken. The ideal would be to state that the value of parameter X is Y. However, since this would require an infinite amount of testing, the parameters are estimated with a given confidence level and precision.

Due to the number of parameters to be estimated, a single parameter is selected for each of the access/disengagement tests and the user information transfer tests that is to be measured with the specified confidence level and precision. This parameter is called the most important performance parameter (MIPP). For this experiment, the access/disengagement parameter selected is the Access Time. For the user information transfer test, the parameter selected is the Bit Error Probability. These parameters will be estimated with a confidence level of 95%, a relative precision of 50% for the Bit Error Probability and an absolute precision of 0.1 seconds for the Access Time.

The remaining parameters, with the exception of the User Information Bit Transfer Rate and the User Fraction of the Input/Output Rate,⁴ use the same number of samples as the selected parameters, resulting in a precision that is greater or less than the specified precision.

4.3 Test Equipment

Figure 2 shows the ITS test equipment configurations used for collecting sample data in the data extraction phase. The test equipment at each site includes

- a workstation with data extraction software
- a Basic Rate Interface (BRI) terminal adapter
- an X.25 packet assembler/disassembler
- 9.6 kbps modems
- satellite clock receivers
- an Integrated Services Digital Network (ISDN) mini-PBX with 2 BRI and 2 Primary Rate Interface (PRI) cards
- an ACTS ISDN interface.

For the PEP, both the receive and transmit test sets remain at the ITS facility (i.e., the test runs in a loop-back mode).

The workstations run on-line application programs, designed by ITS, that act as the "users." The data extraction software, written in C, creates a session between the transmitting user's test-set (the source) and the receiving user's test-set (the destination) as seen in Figure 2. The order of events that the software implements is

Figure 2. Preliminary experiment equipment setup.

1. The source software initializes and opens all the appropriate output files and arrays.
2. The source software places a call, through the ES (T1-VSAT) and ACTS, to the destination, logs on, and starts the destination's software program. Each event is time tagged using a time stamp generated by the GOES satellite clock receiver.
3. The destination software initializes and opens all the appropriate output files and arrays and sends a "READY" back to the source when initialization is finished. Each event is time tagged.
4. The source software transmits a predetermined number of pseudo-random data blocks to the destination and time tags the start and end of the transferred blocks.
5. When the source has transmitted all the data, it initiates disengagement for itself and the destination and writes all the time tags to the appropriate files.
6. The destination software saves and time tags the received data in a buffer, writes the data and times to a file when it sees the "end of data transfer" character, and logs off when the source logoff sequence is received.

These application programs measure the performance of the access and disengagement parameters in a separate run from the user information transfer parameters. The main difference is in the way the time stamps are taken for the two tests. Since the amount of data transferred is not important for the access/disengagement test, the number of transferred data blocks is set to a minimum (1 block) and the number of access/disengagement attempts is the number of trials necessary

to obtain a given precision. Similarly, for user information transfer tests, the number of access/disengagement attempts is set to a minimum (1 access/disengagement attempt) and the number of blocks transferred (at 4000+ bytes/block) is the number of trials necessary to obtain a given precision.

When the tests are completed, the data and time-stamp files are transferred to a workstation server which contains the data reduction and analysis programs. These programs, written in FORTRAN, determine the level of performance obtained during the extraction period. Basically, they analyze the time stamps, event states, and any differences between the transmitted and received data to estimate the performance parameter values.

4.4 Test Order and Length

The preliminary experiment will be run from the ITS ES back to the ITS ES, at a low traffic level (since this is an experimental system, it is assumed that the normal traffic level is "low"), and in clear weather (i.e., no propagation impairment). The tests will be run for all three services which consist of

1. circuit switching over the B-channel,
2. packet switching over the B-channel, and
3. low-speed data rate transfer using a modem (9600 baud).

These three tests will be run for both the access/disengagement tests and the user information transfer tests so there will be a total of six tests. Since there are only three tests for each function and since only one factor is changing, the order of the tests is not important. Chosen randomly, the order of the tests will be 3, 1, 2.

For each service/user information transfer function combination, the test will run for approximately 30 seconds (not counting access time). This accounts for 40 blocks of 4096 bytes each. Ideally, the test should last 20.5 seconds. However, due to overhead, the user data will not transfer at the full 64 kbps, so the transfer time will take longer than ideally possible. For each service/access/disengagement function combination, the test will consist of 40 access/disengagement attempts. The amount of time that it takes to run each test is unknown. With the setup currently used, each access attempt takes approximately 10 seconds. Assuming similar timing, the test will take approximately 400 seconds or 6 minutes 40 seconds.

Forty trials were chosen for both the access/disengagement tests and the user information transfer tests since it is assumed that 40 trials will be sufficient. At the conclusion of the test, it can be determined if this assumption was correct or if more trials (samples) are necessary. In addition, it can be determined if fewer trials can be used to obtain the required precision, thus decreasing the test and satellite time.

Determination of the number of required tests to obtain a given precision at the stated 95% confidence level requires calculating

the sample mean, standard deviation and autocorrelation coefficient of lag 1 of the PEP's sample data⁵. These are found by analyzing the reduced data, consisting of time or failure probability sample values, x_i . The sample mean, \bar{x} , is defined by

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n'} \sum_{i=1}^{n'} x_i \quad (1)$$

where n' is the number of tests performed. The sample variance, σ_m^2 , is given by

$$\sigma_m^2 = \frac{1}{n'-1} \sum_{i=1}^{n'} (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \quad (2)$$

The sample standard deviation is the square root of (2). The autocorrelation coefficient of lag 1, ρ_1 , is given by

$$\rho_1 = \frac{1}{\sigma_m^2(n'-1)} \sum_{i=1}^{n'-1} (x_i - \bar{x})(x_{i+1} - \bar{x}) \quad (3)$$

These parameters are calculated by the analysis software routines, called by the script *dopre*. Once these values are known, the number of required tests, n , to obtain an absolute precision a , is given by

$$n = \left(\frac{z_\alpha \sigma_m}{a} \right)^2 \left(\frac{1 + \rho_1}{1 - \rho_1} \right) \quad (4)$$

where z_α depends on the confidence level. For a confidence level of 95%, z_α is 1.96, while for a confidence level of 90%, z_α is 1.645. References [7, Vol. 2 pp. 15-18] and [8] provide the origination of these values.

5. Schedule

The experiment time for the PEP consists of 5 hours per week for 4 weeks. The time per week is split into 3 hours one day and 2 hours another day. The days requested from NASA were Monday and Wednesday each week.

The schedule for the first week is

- Monday - run the access/disengagement 9.6 kbps modem test through the satellite.
- Tuesday - reduce the data from Monday.
- Wednesday - run the user information transfer 9.6 kbps modem test.
- Thursday - reduce the data from Wednesday.

The schedule for the second week is the same as above with the exception that the ISDN circuit mode tests are run. Similarly,

the third week is the same as above with the exception that the X.25 mode tests are run. The fourth week is saved for running additional tests as necessary (e.g., to obtain the required precision or to correct problems encountered with previous weeks' tests).

6.0 References

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1. The signal-to-noise ratio gave the user an idea of how reliably the data would be received and the bandwidth gave the user an idea of how fast data could be transmitted.

2. The reference event names shown in Table 1 are defined in the revision of ANSI X3.102 that is currently being reviewed for approval.

3. For the ITS ACTS experiment, the disengagement parameters are split into source and destination disengagement, so that the amount of time to tear down the connection is evaluated for both users. Separating disengagement into two parts results in 24 performance parameters.

4. Since precision requires multiple samples, and the User Information Bit Transfer Rate and User Fraction of Input/Output Rate only result in one sample per test, it is impossible to discuss precision with respect to these parameters.

5. The autocorrelation coefficient of lag 1 is the correlation coefficient for a discrete random process taken with itself displaced in time by one sample.